

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE PROCESS OF ADAPTING TO HIGHER EDUCATION

Abdukarimov Jaxongir Maxamadjon o‘g‘li,
Andijan State Pedagogical Institute
Teacher of the Department of “Pedagogy and Psychology”
Jahongirshox711@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19417379>

Annotation: A country that does not take care of children and youth has no future, and unless there are significant changes in the near future, we are doomed to extinction. Youth is a socio-demographic group experiencing social maturity, adaptation to the adult world, and future changes. Young people have fluid boundaries of their age, they depend on socio-economic development of society, the level of culture, living conditions. To consider the problems of youth, it is necessary to imagine what youth is, how it differs from other social groups.

Key words: youth, psychological factors, adaptation, education.

Youth is only a relatively independent unity. It is divided into different groups with their own characteristics, difficulties, problems, which differ from each other position in the system of social production, the real contribution to the development of society, as well as the level of consciousness, the nature of interests, needs, lifestyle and place of residence. Youth, when everyone must determine their own destiny, find the only true, leading to success way of life, which will allow maximum realization of their abilities and talents. This is a period associated with an excruciatingly difficult process of self-discovery, finding your own "I". A person needs to define the boundaries of his real abilities, to understand what he is capable of, to assert himself in society. On the other hand, at the same time he needs to form the most accurate idea of the world around him, to systematize value orientations, political, moral, aesthetic views. Life puts the young person before the need to make a number of critical decisions in the context of the lack of life experience. The choice of profession, the choice of a life partner, the choice of friends - this is not a complete list of problems, one or another decision which to a large extent forms the image of the subsequent life [3].

The ability to adapt to the requirements of the emerging information society is largely determined by the peculiarities of the psychology and social position of young people.

Problems of adaptation to various conditions of social existence directly concern the young generation of our country. It is known that a significant period of adolescence passes in the process of peculiar types of learning activities. Humanitarization of education, aimed at the development, mastering and use of humanitarian knowledge for the awareness of the attitude to the surrounding world and himself, his independent activity in this world, creates the necessary basis for the optimization of the process of adaptation of young people to various forms of learning [1].

The peculiarity of the modern system of higher professional education is the presence of a number of contradictions:

- between the readiness of first-year students of higher education institutions for learning in the new system and the requirements of this system for first-year students, which determine the need for rapid adaptation of students to the educational process of the university;

- between the need for rapid and effective adaptation of first-year students and the undeveloped system of activities providing pedagogical support during the adaptation to the educational process of the university;

The analysis of literary sources allows us to state that the problem of first-year students' adaptation to the educational process of the university remains insufficient. Most of the publications related to the adaptation in the conditions of higher education refer to the social or professional aspects of adaptation [4]. Such aspects of the problem as a comprehensive approach to the process of first-year students' adaptation to the conditions of studying at the university, formation of pedagogical measures, determination of their content, forms, methods and means that contribute to the efficiency of the adaptation process need to be solved. Thus, obviously, there is a theoretical and practical problem, which is formulated as follows: what are the features and optimal pedagogical conditions of students' adaptation to study at the university? Higher education institutions are that micro environment in which a young person without irreversible negative processes, personal deformation can pass from childhood non-self to adult independent life[2].

Pedagogical teams of universities are always concerned about the problems of adaptation of freshmen, developing whole systems to help yesterday's schoolboy to overcome contradictions between his available "capital" and qualitatively new requirements in an educational institution. The yesterday's schoolboy gets into a different environment when he crosses the threshold of the university: lectures, lectures, lectures. When the seminars begin, it turns out that you can not always prepare for them. In general, it is not necessary to learn, solve, memorize something every day.

As a result there often appears an opinion about the seeming ease of studying at the university in the first semester, there is a certainty of catching up and mastering everything before the session, there is a careless attitude towards learning. The payback comes in the session. And then, not passing all the exams, not getting credit, the student who does not have a high capacity for work, self-organization and high motivation just loses faith in himself and interest in learning[6].

In studies of the process of adaptation of first-year students to university, the following main difficulties are usually highlighted: negative experiences associated with the departure of yesterday's students from the school team with its mutual help and moral support; uncertainty of motivation to choose a profession, insufficient psychological preparation for it; inability to exercise psychological self-regulation of behavior and activity, exacerbated by the lack of the habit of daily control of teachers; the search for the optimal mode of work and rest in the new conditions; the adjustment of everyday life and self-care, especially during the transition from home to the dormitory; lack of skills of independent work, the inability to take notes, work with primary sources, dictionaries, reference books, pointers.

Personal development of the student in high school is not only the development of intelligence, but also the readiness for autonomy, independence, the formation of a positive attitude to the world and acceptance of others, the formation of self-confidence, motivation for self-actualization, and self-improvement. These problems are especially acute in the first years of training in the period of adaptation to the conditions of the university [7].

In order to work out tactics and strategies to ensure optimal adaptation of a student to the university, it is important to know the life plans and interests of a first year student, the system of dominant motives, the level of pretensions, self-esteem, the ability to consciously regulate behavior, etc. The successful solution of this problem is connected with the development of the psychological service of the university.

References

1. Danilicheva N. A., Balakireva L. A. Psychology of professional choice. SPb., 1998. p 105 .
2. Zimnyaya I. A. Pedagogical psychology. Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 1997. p 480 .
3. Meerson F.Z. Adaptation, stress and prevention. M., 1981. p 278 .
4. Orlov, M. M. Ascent to individuality. M., 1991. p 287 .

5. Repkin V. V., Repkin G. V., Zaika E. V. About a system of psychological and pedagogical monitoring in the construction of learning activity // *Voprosy psixologii*. 1995. № 1. P. 13-24.
6. G. Sellier. *Stress without distress*. Moscow: "RENAR" and Central Committee of Russian Red Cross Society. 1992. P. 15.
7. Solomatina T.B. *Social adaptation of students in the process of professional education*. M., 2001. P. 3-18.